

DATA ANALYSIS REPORT ON EFFECT OF PREGNANCY AND NEWBORN CASES DUE TO COVID 19

(JAYDIP DATTA)

ABSTRACT : In this report the effect of Covid19 on pregnant mother and baby is represented .The different stages of maternal mortality , ICU admitted cases , Preterm birth ,Still birth , Newborn death for Covid with respect to NonCovid cases are considered . Theoretical frequency fraction (Covid : NonCovid) is to be considered with frequency fraction obtained from the result

KEYWORDS : Covid19 , Pregnancy , Newborn , Preterm Birth , Frequency fraction , Risk factor

METHODS :

	Covid	NonCovid
Maternal Mortality	0	11
ICU	0	42
Preterm Birth	44	295
Still Birth	0	0
Neonatal Death	0	0
NICU	38	64

1. Data availability (1) – Figure 1

A tabular representation of [6 x 2] data (1) matrix stating from maternal death to newborn ICU cases .

2. Data Analysis – Bar graph [Figure -2] and 3D- Plot [Figure -3]

Figure -2 (3,4)

Figure – 3 (4,5)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Figure 2 presents a bar chart for all the cases (1,2) as described in Figure 1. Figure -3 is a contour representation ie density of infection of the same cases. From both the Figure -2 (3,4) and Figure -3 (4,5) the trend shows that for maternal mortality of Covid death increases from zero to ICU cases reaches to **maximum for preterm birth cases (nine quarter months approx)** and then suddenly fall down to zero for still birth and neonatal death cases then again increases to NICU Covid cases .

Theoretical frequency fraction(Covid / NonCovid) (1) also a measure of probability (427 /1121) = 0.381 vs frequency fraction (Covid/NonCovid) obtained from result = (82 /412) = 0.199 means a risk factor of 0.52 of pregnant mother and child due to Covid19 infection .

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